

Focus Group and Survey Report on the Role of Libraries During Crises

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List of Abbreviations

The following table presents the acronyms used in the deliverable in alphabetical order.

Abbreviations	Description
European Union	EU
Higher Education	HE
Higher education institution	HEI
Information-psychological operation	IPSO
Research Question	RQ
Ukraine	UA
Work Package	WP

Executive Summary

This report presents the key findings of a Ukrainian thematic study conducted as part of the Caelum project, which explores the role of university libraries during crises. The report is based on data collected during focus group discussions with the academic community (teachers, students, librarians) and stakeholders, as well as a nationwide online survey conducted in Ukraine. The combination of quantitative and qualitative methods provides valuable insights into how libraries have responded to crises, what expectations different stakeholder groups have of libraries in times of turmoil, and what challenges affect their ability to respond effectively.

The results are thematically structured around the project's research questions, which highlight the actual and potential roles of libraries in crisis situations, perceptions of user needs, institutional constraints, and opportunities for civic engagement. The study also focuses on the role of libraries in countering disinformation in emergency situations in Ukraine, as this is the subject of a selected thematic study by the Ukrainian State University of Science and Technologies, which will be explored in greater depth in the next stages of the project.

It is assumed that in times of crisis, the university library becomes a centre of open innovation in education, science, social support and culture. These open innovations and partnerships can influence the role of libraries during and after a crisis. These are opportunities that could strengthen the role of libraries in promoting individual, academic and community resilience during the crisis and Ukraine's recovery.

Based on the results obtained, it is emphasised that the crisis has been an impetus for change, and a list of recommendations is proposed to strengthen the role of libraries in times of severe hardship.

About the project

CAELUM (Open science supporting vulnerable communities: empowering university libraries in crisis response, 2025-2027, <https://caelum.ut.ee/>) is a 2-year Erasmus+ project that places university libraries in the forefront of crisis response through open science, supporting vulnerable communities and bolstering EU-UA cooperation. Through a series of activities, CAELUM aims to up-skill university libraries' staff in innovative and interdisciplinary approaches to crisis response and promote and sustain university libraries-driven open knowledge and civic engagement among HE students and staff for crisis response. Thus, CAELUM empowers university libraries in leveraging open and citizen science approaches as well as community engagement practices for crisis response in multiple contexts.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

This report presents the main findings of a study of the Ukrainian case conducted as part of the Caelum project, which investigates how university libraries support communities during crises. The data was collected through an online survey targeting the academic community (teachers, students, librarians) and stakeholders – members of the wider community who are in some way connected to libraries and higher education in different regions of Ukraine. Together, these sources paint a picture of how libraries have coped with previous crises, offer an understanding of the expectations of different target groups during crisis periods, and the challenges libraries face in trying to meet the needs of their users.

1.2 Scope

This report presents the results of WP2A2 from the USUST, a partner of the CAELUM project. The USUST coordinated the collection of anonymous data, conducted an online survey (n=72), and held a focus group discussion with the participation of 14 participants representing a diverse mix of the academic community (n=8) (teachers, students, librarians) and stakeholders (n=6) – members of a wider community who are in one way or another related to libraries and higher education (representatives of public and expert organisations, local governments, journalists) from different regions of Ukraine. Visually, the data is shown in the figure 1.

Figure 1. The role of the participant in the academic community.

The importance of the intergenerational perspective lies in the fact that respondents' age influences perceptions and needs for educational and digital services. Respondents from all stakeholder groups represented a wide age range. The largest group were respondents aged 36...45 years old (n = 26), followed by those of 18...25 years old (n = 24). Respondents aged 46...60 years old made up a small part (n = 15), and a slightly lower number of 26...35 years old (n = 14). (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Age group of participants.

At the same time, when conducting online surveys and focus groups, it was crucial for researchers to expand the demographic data of respondents about their areas of residence or temporary stay in Ukraine during wartime.

For instance, involving respondents from different regions that are directly affected by the war's consequences is important for several reasons: (1) Regional variability of experience: different regions of Ukraine experience different scales of military impact, which is reflected in the specifics of requests to libraries; (2) Ensuring representativeness: this allows to identify a wider range of needs and challenges, which is important for identifying universal but flexible solutions; (3) Obtaining the views of vulnerable groups: particularly, people who have been evacuated or are internally displaced persons (IDPs), which allows considering the experience of marginalised communities in crisis analysis.

The data on the respondents' place of residence or temporary stay in Ukraine are as follows. The largest number of respondents was from the South-east region of Ukraine (n = 32), followed by the Northern Ukraine (n = 15). Slightly fewer respondents were from the Western Ukraine (n = 12), followed by the Eastern Ukraine (n = 10). (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Territory of residence of participants or their temporary stay in Ukraine.

Ukrainian researchers received important data on the type of crisis that had the greatest impact on respondents. At the same time, respondents could indicate several crises.

Most responses from the survey participants are "War or armed conflict" (n = 66; 91.7%). A much lower number of respondents noted that this was the "Mental health or well-being challenges in academic life" crisis (n=34; 47.2%). A slightly lower number of answers – the "Disinformation during emergencies (e.g. war, disasters)" crisis (n=33; 45.8%). The fourth place is occupied by the "Crisis of the state and quality of the environment" (n=22; 30.6%). The next is the "Information overload and challenges related to open science in research" crisis (n=21; 29,2%). The lowest number is the "Climate related crisis (e.g. heatwave, drought, flooding)" (n=5; 6.9%). (Figure 4).

Figure 4. What type of crisis has affected you the most?

In the context of the study, it was important to gain an understanding of "How do you usually find information during a crisis?". The data obtained from the answers (n=72) prove that a significant majority of participants prefer social networks (n=67; 93.1%). In second place as a channel of communication are friends / family (n=53; 73.6%). In third place are news media (n=48; 66.1%). Further, the same indicators are demonstrated by government and university websites or communication (n=33; 45.8%). Fewer respondents choose academic journals or research sources (n=23; 31.9%). Next are library channels (n=16; 22.2%). The last place with the same number of answers – Websites of public associations (NGOs) and Blogs and video blogs (n=1; 1.4%). (Figure 5).

Figure 5. How do you usually find information during a crisis?

We can gain insight into how university libraries are treated in crises, what challenges they face, and what the expectations of their communities and stakeholders as users are, only with the help of the collected extended data.

Although the main objective of WP2A2 was to investigate the general roles and perceptions of crisis response, and the basic questions were developed and agreed upon in advance at the consortium level, the USUST appended the implementation of this case study with a number of other questions related to the crisis of disinformation in emergencies, as this topic is the subject of the case study that the USUST implements in WP3 through the combined (national-level) institutional and community initiatives in the context of the academic library.

1.3 Research questions

This report addresses the following research questions defined by the CAELUM consortium:

- **RQ1:** What has been the libraries' role during crises?
- **RQ2:** What are the expectations and perceived needs of students, academic staff, and library professionals regarding library support in crisis situations?
- **RQ3:** What barriers and gaps have university libraries faced in responding to crises?
- **RQ4:** How can university libraries contribute to public engagement and community resilience during and after crises?

The USUST added a question related to the crisis of disinformation in emergencies to the implementation of the case study, as the "The Crisis of Disinformation in Emergency Conditions: The Library in Preventing the Social, Civil and Political Consequences of Environmental Safety Misinformation" topic is the subject of the case study that USUST implements in WP3 through combined institutional and community initiatives in the context of the academic library.

USUST-RQ: What experience and perception of the disinformation crisis in emergencies among the academic community and stakeholders may influence future library practices?

1.4. Structure

The report has the following structure:

- **Section 2** A methodology is outlined, including participant profiles and data collection tools.
- **Section 3** Key findings of the survey and focus groups organized by relevant topics are presented.

- **Section 4** Problems and opportunities of libraries responding to crises are discussed.
- **Section 5** Considering the results of the survey and focus group the conclusions are drawn.

2. Methodology

This section has the following structure:

- **2.1** Data Collection: Focus Group, Online Survey
- **2.2** Data Analysis
- **2.3** Ethical considerations

To answer the proposed research questions, a mixed-methods strategy was applied, combining quantitative and qualitative data collection through online surveys and focus group discussions.

Quantitative trends, general sentiment and personal experience of respondents were obtained through the online survey; thanks to focus groups, it was possible to capture the emotional colouring, qualitative understanding of life experience, hidden motives of expectations, which remain outside the framework of formalized questionnaires. The application of both methods contributed to a deeper understanding of the needs of users and those institutional challenges that libraries can respond effectively to in times of crises.

To collect and analyse the data of the focus group discussion, as well as answers to open-ended questions of the online survey, an inductive thematic analysis (ITA) was used, adapted to the crisis context (a threat to human health and life, disconnections of communication, lack of funds to pay for automatic commercial services, etc.). The ITA methodology was adapted as follows:

- Flexible format for data collection and analysis: participation in the focus group (online) was allowed using asynchronous interviews or text responses in secure messengers for those who could not be present in real time (air raid alert, start of bombing, moving to shelters, disconnections of communication, etc.)
- Heightened ethical sensitivity: the psychological state of the participants is considered; the possibility of anonymous expression of opinions (written notes) is provided.
- Focus on practical experience: shifting the emphasis from generalized ideas to specific cases of behaviour in the context of various aspects of crises.
- Use of freeware tools to process and analyse data under conditions of the lack of funds

2.1. Data Collection: Focus Group, Online Survey

The peculiarities of organising, conducting and obtaining relevant data of the **Focus Groups survey** in Ukraine during the crisis of the highest level – the war, are the conducting of two focus groups (an academic and stakeholders). The total number of participants is 14 people. Participants of the academic focus group (n=8): representatives of the academic community (teachers-researchers, students, librarians) from different regions of Ukraine. Participants of the stakeholders group (n=6): members of the wider community who are in one way or another related to libraries and higher education (representatives of public and expert organisations, local governments, journalists) from different regions of Ukraine.

This decision of the Ukrainian team is related to: (1) providing an opportunity for each participant to actively participate in the discussion in a fairly short period of time; (2) creating optimally favourable conditions for participants who have traumatic experiences in a comfortable and convenient online environment; (3) providing quality communication and technical support in case of shelling in different regions of Ukraine through voice messages or text responses in secure messengers; (4) obtaining independent opinions from participants, given the increased ethical sensitivity in cases of traumatic experiences (e.g., loss of housing or evacuation) and the dynamics of each group.

Each group (academic and stakeholders) consisted of participants purposefully selected to provide a variety of life experience and professional training. Each of the participants had a traumatic crisis experience, so the knowledge and opinions they shared are especially valuable.

Focus Group discussions were held on the ZOOM platform, which allows users to communicate via video and audio, exchange messages and files. The working language is Ukrainian.

On May 23, 2025, a discussion was held in the stakeholders focus group. 6 respondents participated in this discussion (2 – representatives of the public, 2 – environmental specialists, 2 – investigative journalists). The discussion was moderated by 1 moderator.

On May 30, 2025, a discussion was held in an academic focus group with the participation of 8 participants (3 students, 3 research teachers, 1 librarian-scientist, 1 library director). The discussion was moderated by 1 moderator. Organisational and technical support – 1 person.

The basic questions for the focus group were developed and agreed upon in advance at the consortium level. The USUST appended the basic questions with the "The crisis of disinformation in an emergency" question (Annex I), related to the subject of the case study that the USUST implements in WP3 – "The Crisis of Disinformation in Emergency

Conditions: The Library in Preventing the Social, Civil and Political Consequences of Environmental Safety Misinformation."

The discussion of both focus groups was recorded on video. Free tools were used to process Zoom video recordings. Transcripts were manually checked, confidential data was anonymised, and then the video and audio recordings were deleted. After conducting the focus groups, anonymous feedback was received from all 14 participants ([USUST - Focus group Feedback Participants FORM](#)).

Online Survey. An all-Ukrainian anonymous online survey to study the role that university libraries can and should play in moments of turmoil was conducted using Google Form from 22.05.2025 to 05.06.2025. Information about the survey was disseminated through the website of the USUST Scientific Library, on Facebook (pages of the USUST Scientific Library, the Section of University Libraries of the Ukrainian Library Association and other public associations). The survey at the national level was conducted in Ukrainian.

As in the case of the focus group, the basic questions for the online survey were developed and agreed upon in advance at the consortium level. The USUST has added to the implementation of this case study a few questions related to the crisis of disinformation in emergencies, as this topic is the subject of the case study that the USUST implements in WP3. The Background information block was appended with a few questions, and the answer options were extended; moreover, the block V: "THE CRISIS OF DISINFORMATION IN AN EMERGENCY" (open and closed questions) was added. (Annex II - [USUST - Questionnaire questions](#)).

It took 10-15 minutes to complete the survey. In total, we received 72 responses.

2.2 Data Analysis

The use of a flexible method of qualitative research – Inductive thematic analysis (ITA) of data, was adapted for the crisis context of Ukrainian participants in the focus group discussion, as well as answers to open-ended questions of the online survey. (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The researchers read through the data multiple times and carefully re-read the focus group transcripts, notes, and written comments in chat and messengers to understand the overall context. The inductive approach allowed these topics to emerge and be constructed through exploratory interpretation based on the data itself, without the use of a pre-existing pattern (topics) coding system. The topics that represented, for instance, recurring ideas and needs, were developed through handwritten and visual summaries that grouped related responses.

The quantitative data of the survey were processed using Excel-based tables ([USUST - Answers of online survey respondents](#)). Descriptive statistics, such as frequency and percentages, were calculated to summarize general trends. Since it is not possible to

highlight emotional or empirical nuances in closed-ended questions (multiple-choice), the statistical results were complemented and contextualized by thematically summarized responses to open-ended online survey questions.

2.3 Ethical considerations

The participants of the online survey and focus group discussion were informed about the CAELUM project, its goals, where and how the data will be collected, used and anonymized. ([USUST - Questionnaire questions](#) & [USUST - Focus group questions](#)). The questions stated for the participants were pre-agreed upon by all CAELUM project partners. The informed consent form for the focus group discussion was sent to the participants by e-mail in advance. The content of the informed consent form was additionally presented to the participants before the focus group discussion began, and all participants confirmed their understanding by signing the form.

3. Findings and discussion

This section combines the survey results and focus groups under thematic headings, each of which answers one of the four leading research questions of the CAELUM project and a USUST-specific question. Quantitative results and qualitative reflections are combined to provide a holistic interpretation of the data.

3.1. The Role of Libraries During Crisis

The peculiarity of university libraries in Ukraine is their purpose as an educational, scientific, informational, and cultural structural department of HEI. That is, in addition to numerous main tasks related to supporting educational activities and scientific research, librarians are also involved in the organisation of particular spare time practices (including cultural entertainment), which provide students with the opportunity to escape from sometimes routine life, daily education load or worries, and contribute to the expansion of knowledge, skills, self-realisation, a sense of belonging and communality. (Kolesnykova, T., & Demidko, M., 2024)

University libraries in Ukraine enjoy the constant trust of the academic community, providing information and service support for the continuity of education and science under conditions of instability. Thus, the last 10 years of adaptation to the challenges of not only digital transformation, but also the permanent Russian-Ukrainian war since 2014 in Crimea and Donbas, political and economic instability and the Covid 2019 period, have laid the foundation for the resilience and effective operation of libraries even in times of crisis.

This was noted by the participants of the focus group discussion, both representatives of the academic community (teachers-researchers, students, librarians) and stakeholders.

They have a clear positive impression of the response (assistance) of libraries to at least one crisis. For example, speaking about trust, respondents have already had experience in library support and therefore note that the services of libraries in crisis (wartime) are multidirectional:

"Since the Covid 2019 period, our university library has begun to apply psychological support online. It was important, and it was a certain experience of both resilience and weakening of resistance."

"Since the beginning of the war, the library's underground book depositories have been used by both the university community and residents as shelters and "places of calm". Here people hide during air raid alerts, read books, talk with librarians on various topics. The cosy atmosphere contributes to the creativity "burst" of the community. Poetry, drawing, handicrafts, and other creative activities of students and teachers of various faculties were supported by the library. Large library shelters host not only university events, but also city and national ones: chess tournaments, art workshops, psychological trainings, international conferences."

"As a student, a future historian, I have experience in two crises. At first, it was Covid, problems related to health, family and remoteness. Then a full-scale war began, and many relatives and friends of mine went abroad to save their children. But in cases of both crises, I always received help from my library both online and in its locations. This is how I felt that I was not alone and that I was involved in the university community."

"Familiar things, such as remotely obtaining a UDC for an article or access to Scopus, using resources online or a remote consultation, evoke a sense of stability and orderliness in the life of a researcher."

"... The library is a kind of "co-working". After 2022, when several institutions and public organizations were relocated from the occupied or frontline territories, we used some library premises as a "workplace" with light, Internet, and ability to continue working and communicating. Additionally, the practice of benefactors to donate modern books in Ukrainian to replenish the book fund has intensified. And this has become a kind of bonus for libraries and for readers."

In most cases, when talking about a positive library experience during a crisis, respondents focus on two aspects – social and academic. The social aspect was more emphasized by respondents from "The West of Ukraine" region and "The North of Ukraine" region. The academic aspect was more emphasized by respondents from "The South-East of Ukraine" region and "The East of Ukraine" region.

At the same time, positive library experience during the crisis was confirmed by respondents with different ages and different roles in the academic community and stakeholders related to it.

The statistical results of the online survey were not so unambiguous. Thus, to the question "Have you ever received support from the library during the crisis?" the answers of 72 respondents were distributed as follows: "Yes" (n=34; 47.2%); "No" (n=24; 33.3%); "Not sure" (n=14; 19.4%).

Open (optional) positive answers ("Yes") varied. On the one hand, respondents, noting the variety of support for the friendly and caring university library staff, emphasised the

social aspect of assistance. For example, organising and holding joint events for internally displaced persons (IDPs) in the safe space of the library, emotional support, consultations with psychologists, group art therapy trainings for adults, and master classes for children of teachers, employees, IDPs, participating in children's master classes, organising the joint events of students, public activists, volunteers in environmental actions, etc.

On the other hand, respondents were satisfied with the academic aspect of the various library services they received online to provide an opportunity to teach, research, and learn during the war. For example, free access to Scopus & WoS scientometric databases, the opportunity to work with paid publications for free on the Research4Life portal, consulting assistance in obtaining media literacy skills for family members of the university community; involvement of teachers as lecturers in information culture for career guidance events for schoolchildren, participation of students in library video projects, etc.

At the same time, the analysis of the results of the online survey shows that, despite the trust in the library, respondents do not choose it as the first source of information during the crisis. That is, users can believe in the importance of the library but still turn to other sources when immediate information is needed. This is the so-called "passive" trust, without real priority information interaction or critical attitude. The answers to the question "How do you usually find information during a crisis?" prove that library channels (n=16; 22.2%) are significantly inferior to social networks (n=67; 93.1%), friends/family (n=53; 73.6%), and news media (n=48; 66.1%). It is a challenge for libraries to work to ensure that "passive" trust turns into real behaviour.

Thus, there is some contradiction between the existing community trust in libraries and some uncertainty of strategic ways to increase the role of library channels as important information sources in times of crisis.

3.2. Expectations and Needs

This subsection is devoted to the analysis of the types of support expected by representatives of the academic community and stakeholders from libraries in crises. It outlines key priorities, a request for services, and a vision for how libraries can strengthen their preparedness for future challenges.

Analysis of the survey statistics shows that respondents' expectations during the crisis are as follows: "Online library services" (e-books, databases, etc.) prevail (n=55; 76.4%). The next is "Physical space for study/work" (n=48; 66.7%). A slightly lower result is "Internet or Wi-Fi" (n=45; 62.5%). This is followed by "Trainings and courses" (n=42; 58.3%). The next is "Cultural events and social interaction" (n=40; 55.6%). There is also an option to answer "I would not expect anything from libraries" (n=14; 19.4%) (Figure 6).

Figure 6. In a crisis situation, which forms of support would you expect or seek from a library?

The answers to the open-ended questions of the online survey, what can help the library create services and a space for support and safety in a crisis, were quite concise:

"Safe space. Support of the university management. Trained staff. Direct contacts with representatives of all structural departments and students. Adapted services. Psychosocial support. Partnership. Technical resources. Focus on the needs of the community".

"Young staff, the ability to communicate with different categories of users, computer and information technology skills, quick response to changes and financial incentives."

"Expanding the cooperation with experts of public associations, local journalists and university specialists to receive comments on special topics to create podcasts, posters, short informational messages."

Focus group respondents represent their expectations (often very emotional) as follows:

"A library can be a kind of "Point of Invincibility", where there are various opportunities: recharge the phone, get a stable connection, find out the current action plan (e.g., in the face of the danger of chemical and radiation threats) and other information services."

"Some libraries have full-fledged underground book depositories. I believe that these premises can be used to create additional spaces of safety and tranquillity for learning and hosting social events."

"The University Library can expand international communication, participate in joint projects of libraries in Ukraine and abroad, and collaborate with professional public organisations from different countries. There are so many points of contact."

"As a teacher in times of crisis, I want libraries to be as involved as possible in the information support of remote learning and to bring some innovation."

"My participation in the regional student organisation and numerous volunteer actions formed a clear vision of the need to support young people and people with disabilities (unfortunately, the number of the latter is increasing due to the war)."

Young people aged 18...25 years old and age group of 26...35 years old are active in their proposals. The territory of their residence or temporary stay is the region of the South-East of Ukraine and the region of the Western Ukraine. Using various examples, the participants of the discussion demonstrate that in times of crisis and the spread of disinformation, access to verified information and instructions for action is extremely important for the population. This informational and social function can be performed by the university library in cooperation with specialized scientists of higher education institutions, with experts of public organisations, and public libraries of the region.

3.3. Barriers and Gaps

Of course, the data obtained on the expectations of communities in the context of forms of the library support in times of crisis are a kind of "beacons" in the twilight of military life. But, to follow the light of these "beacons", researchers must have a big picture of the present regarding the barriers and gaps that university libraries faced in response to crises.

The online survey answers to the question "Do you feel comfortable turning to the library for help in a crisis?" show that most respondents (n=72) say "Yes" (n=42; 58.3%). However, the rate of those who are "not sure" is quite remarkable (n=24; 33.3%). Say "No" (n=6; 8.3%). (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Would you feel comfortable approaching a library for help in crisis?

But the analysis of respondents' answers to this open question about "No" or "Not sure" shows that they understood the phrase "Feel comfortable" as a different connotation, because they mostly wrote: "I did not apply", "I did not know that the library could help me in a crisis".

The specific reasons (barriers) in most cases are as follows (Figure 8): • It is difficult to find up-to-date information on the library's website and social networks (n=46; 63.9%); • They did not know that the library could help in a crisis (n=34; 47.2%); • It's difficult to get to the library (n=33; 45.8%).

Figure 8. What might prevent you from using library services in a crisis?

Focus group conversations had different contextual and emotional "colouring": from stating the individual gaps or barriers in the work of libraries during the crisis of the highest level to concern about the direct purpose of the university library – support for learning, teaching, research. Thus, respondents emphasize:

"There is a problem of physical accessibility for students: unfortunately, not all libraries are equipped with ramps. Braille books are needed for those who have poor eyesight, but they are extremely expensive, and special funds need to be raised for this."

"With the beginning of the war, the library expanded the list of social services – exhibitions of local artists, educational events for citizens, thematic meetings, etc. This creates a problem – librarians began to engage in activities that are not typical for their position. These transformations require changes in the staff list, which cannot be officially approved. Social projects and social services should be implemented by professionals whose job description includes such functions. Therefore, I see a risk that libraries will turn into "caches of scientific and technical information" and begin to provide social services. In fact, we have specialists in the positions of "librarians" who are not engaged in their professional activities."

"Barriers can be the library teams themselves, which do not take the initiative to change, wait for the replenishment of the library fund and do not introduce new services, do not actively cooperate. In contrast, we have examples of active libraries that initiate cooperation themselves, actively participate in grants and other initiatives, and offer joint events and projects."

The researchers suggest that since the barriers, gaps, expectations and doubts of users and communities are constantly changing, libraries should rethink their approaches to communication and more actively remind of their diverse capabilities, emphasize their social value and impact.

3.4. Public Engagement and Community Support

This unit analyses how academic libraries maintain interconnection with their communities during crises. The perception of the role of libraries in interaction with the

public, user participation in library initiatives, and expectations and needs for support in emergencies are examined.

Beyond their primary educational, scientific and cultural mission, Ukraine's university libraries can play an important role in supporting societal resilience by mobilising resources, knowledge, and partnerships for the benefit of the community in times of turmoil or unpredictable challenges.

This statement is confirmed by the analysis of survey data and answers the questions: (Figure 9). For example, "Can libraries play an important role in supporting communities during crises?" Assessment of respondents' agreement with this statement: "Strongly agree" (n=22); "Agree" (n=28) and "Agree rather than disagree" (n=21)

Figure 9. Please rate your agreement with several statements.

The participants specified the events: Presentations of research on mental health; trainings for communities "Beware! Explosive Objects!" and "First Medical Aid"; free space for meetings with activists, war veterans and volunteers; group classes with psychologists; presentations of book publications; webinars on openness of knowledge, academic integrity, open educational resources, CC licenses; conducting practical classes on the university library basis; exhibitions of amateur decorative handicrafts; participation in student events organised on the basis of the library, etc.

However, the respondents' answers to the following question somewhat blur this positive picture of high trust in the ability of libraries to work in various formats for the

benefit of communities in times of crisis. Statistical analysis of the answers to the question "Have you ever participated in public events or library events of your university?", proves that: "Yes" (n=44; 61.1%); "Not sure" (n=1; 1.4%). "No" (n=27; 37.5%); that is, these respondents did not confirm their symbolic (as it figured out) trust in the capabilities of libraries in practice.

The fact that people believe in the importance of libraries in times of crisis, but do not always participate in their initiatives, indicates an imbalance between the idea of the library as a pillar of the community and its real functionality in this direction. This means that libraries should work harder to increase their practical visibility and influence in public space.

And what are some examples and suggestions on how to build stronger communities during or after the crisis? This question is answered by focus group participants based on their own crisis experience. The proposals were as follows:

"To intensify communication with various foundations and public foreign organisations, e.g., exchange of experience, holding joint events online, writing articles. There can also be a collaboration between university libraries and public organisations from different countries."

"Expanding cooperation between youth organisations of the region (city) and libraries. We have examples of projects' implementation that can be scaled up: related to a clean city, responding to disinformation, how to protect yourself from any fraud, etc. The library organises joint research on the ecology or mini-history of the city with the involvement of students, working youth, public volunteers, citizen scientists, investigative journalists."

"Constant movement. Any activities and events that are currently taking place in libraries or other places with the participation of libraries and communities become a kind of "points of exchange of opinions, impressions or disclosure of narratives", because citizens of different nationalities often gather and talk "face to face". For example, the Ukrainian-Japanese Centre, the Goethe-Institute, the Ukrainian-Azerbaijani Centre, "Windows into America", etc."

According to the researchers, these answers can be interpreted as follows. A new priority for university libraries is to go beyond the academic environment and actively interact with stakeholders, as well as wider community, especially in times of crisis and war. Military aggression and related challenges have provided university libraries with a historic opportunity to increase the importance of their role in social, psychological, and humanitarian support for the community (district, city, region). However, the implementation of this opportunity requires active actions, determination, perseverance, understanding of the situation, communication skills from library teams (including colleagues in HEI and public organizations from different countries).

3.5. The crisis of disinformation in an emergency

This subsection focuses on the results of the USUST-RQ question "What experience and perception of the disinformation crisis in emergencies among the academic community and stakeholders may influence future library practices?"

Information security issues are of particular importance in times of crisis, because the enemy's information attacks become more intense precisely when society's ability to resist is weakened. The best basis for enemy influence operations is fear, panic, and disorientation of the population.

A form of information warfare is the Information and Psychological Operation (IPSO), which uses various methods of influence, such as propaganda, disinformation, psychological pressure and manipulation of information, to achieve its objectives. Definition of Disinformation: "False information spread in order to deceive people" (Disinformation. Dictionary Cambridge, n. d.).

The crisis of disinformation in an emergency has been the subject of research by online surveys and focus groups. The vast majority of online survey respondents report that they have faced disinformation crises in the last three years of the war in Ukraine: the answer is "Yes" (n=56; 77.8.1%). (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Have you encountered disinformation crises in the last three years of the full-scale war in Ukraine?

Among the most common examples were: • all IPSO waves about radiation (Chornobyl NPP, Zaporizhzhia NPP, Kharkiv neutron source, shells with depleted uranium); • all ISPO waves about mobilisation (mobilisation of students, postgraduates, teachers, women); • information about possible shelling and events at the front.

To some extent, these clarifying thematic data from the open question coincided with the analysed statistics of the online survey. The following thematic aspects of the disinformation crisis in the emergency conditions of the war in Ukraine turned out to be the most common and relevant. (Figure 11). For example: • Actions on the frontline in Ukraine (n=51; 70.8%); • Actions of the population in emergency situations (n=43; 59.7%); • The progress of the war (n=42; 58.3%); • Socio-economic situation (n=37; 51.4%); • Radiation hazard (n=33; 45.8%).

Figure 11. What thematic aspects of the disinformation crisis in the extraordinary conditions of war in Ukraine are the most widespread and relevant?

Respondents provide negative examples of the impact of the disinformation crisis on themselves or their family, such as:

- Panic among older family members who do not know how to verify information;
- My grandmother is always anxious after waves of IPSO in the news or on Viber;
- Quarrels in the family or with colleagues over information;
- This situation leads to psychological exhaustion, a decrease in the level of critical perception of reality, escalates pessimistic moods and panic expectations;
- Panic and purchase of iodine caused by threats to use nuclear weapons;
- After the information about the mobilisation of students, I even wrote an application for academic leave.

Respondents agree that academic libraries can and should play a specific role in countering disinformation. They are centres of relevant information and proven knowledge, teach information literacy, critical thinking, and source evaluation skills.

Among the tools that libraries can use to warn, prevent, or mitigate the effects of a disinformation crisis in the community, 72 respondents chose the following as the most significant:

- Courses on the information search and verification (n=59; 81.9%);
- Information clarifications (n=48; 66.7%);
- Instructions for citizens (n=44; 61.1%);
- Thematic interviews with specialists from the academic community (n=36; 50%).

The analysis of the discussion data of the focus group participants complements the survey data and provides interesting results and suggestions.

I propose to create a Telegram channel for the library. Students have more confidence in what comes from their university. Librarians could simply check the information and write briefly in their Telegram channel about some sensations and the results of their verification – true or fake. Students will be informed and will spread truthful information.

University libraries need to introduce the "stop-fake" direction and work closely with journalism departments that have a better understanding of terminology (fakes, bots, trolls), know how to distinguish between fakes and facts from judgments.

The results of the analysis of the discussion data allowed the researchers to develop a conventional list of five promising library services that, according to the respondents, will help communities fight disinformation.

Proactive library services: (1) preparation of collections of proven information sources; (2) preparation of information brochures (messages) on the actions of the population in the crisis; (3) "workplace" service with access to full-text paid databases of scientific and scientific-technical information.

Reactive library services: (4) preparation and dissemination of information messages and explanations in crisis conditions (the topic is directly related to the social request for information); (5) organisation of informal training of academic communities and the population on the topics of media literacy and fact-checking.

4. Challenges and opportunities for crisis-responsive libraries

This chapter summarizes the findings (see section 3) of the survey and focus group discussions on the main challenges faced by academic libraries in times of crisis, as well as on their potential to strengthen contributions to the resilience of individuals and communities.

The researchers found that the type of crisis that had the greatest impact on respondents was "War or armed conflict" (91.7%). Undoubtedly, the tragic experience of living in a full-scale war, and before that – in a global pandemic, affected the mental health and well-being in the academic life of many Ukrainians. However, the type of crisis 'Mental health or well-being challenges in academic life' (47.2%) was noted by almost half as many respondents. The third most important crisis is "Disinformation during emergencies (e.g. war, disaster, etc.)". The least important crisis for respondents is 'Climate-related crisis (e.g. heatwave, drought, flooding)'.

Generations of people living, studying and working in wartime have adapted to crisis challenges by developing new strategies for communication or obtaining information. Thus, the largest group in the survey were respondents aged 36...45 years old, for whom an important communication channel is the one that: 1) is the most integrated into everyday life, e.g., social networks that combine personal, professional and parental life; 2) convenient, as it provides immediate information, event organisation, and working

communication. The next large group of respondents are those who were 18...25 years old (Generation Z, who grew up with smartphones and social networks, online communication with an instantaneous, emotionally rich connection is natural for them). These two groups are focused on mobility, speed and versatility, which other communication channels (such as websites of universities, libraries, public associations, etc.) often do not provide. Perhaps that's why, when answering the question "How do you usually find information during a crisis?", the vast majority of participants prefer social networks (93.1%). Friends / family (73.6%) are in second place as a communication channel. News media (66.1%) are in third place. Only 22.2% mention library channels in this context.

The analysis of discussions in focus groups involving respondents from different regions of Ukraine, which are the territories of their permanent residence or temporary stay, provided insight into the regional variability of experience. Thus, representatives of the frontline regions that are exposed to a larger scale of military influence (Eastern Ukraine, South-east of Ukraine, Northern Ukraine), sharing their experience of library support in the crisis, mention the use of underground library book depositories (by the university community and local residents) as shelters, "places of calm", as a "workplace" with light, the Internet and the opportunity to continue working, studying and communicating. Participants from a relatively safe region – Western Ukraine (Lviv, Ivano-Frankivsk, Chernivtsi, Zakarpattia regions) speak about the role of the library in the context of a more "peaceful" life: as "physical spaces for reading and activating the imagination", "a comfortable cozy room for thoughtful work with rare documents", "presentations of the work of contemporary writers and poets", "meetings with war veterans".

However, respondents from different regions noted that it was university libraries that initiated offline or online events about the following: non-violent communication; bringing Ukrainian narratives into the international community and conveying the undistorted truth; openness as a rethinking of higher education, academic integrity, etc. In most cases, when talking about the positive library experience during the crisis, respondents from all regions focus on two aspects – social and academic.

Thus, libraries in different regions are gaining their own experience in responding to various crisis events. The task of libraries is to analyse and summarise it and disseminate effective practices to strengthen the resilience of communities, ensure continuous access to information, support education and psychological well-being of users in emergency.

The results of the survey and focus groups show the presence of positive factors in relation to libraries: 1) most of the respondents felt comfortable turning to the library for help in a crisis; 2) rather high user trust in libraries, which is associated not so much with the volume of services provided, but with their value (social, academic or personal) and significance for the community.

At the same time, this community's trust in libraries is often "passive" in nature, with no real primary information interaction or critical attitude. This may be evidence of: • insufficient community awareness of the services; • low visibility of services/events and involvement of community members in them; • the traditional perception of libraries as "comfort zones" rather than units that respond swiftly to crises; • emotional or physical burnout of librarians themselves; • insufficient competence of library staff to work in various crises; • limited funding and resources.

Respondents also express concern about the loss of the direct purpose of university libraries as centres of scientific and technical information and their partial transformation into spaces of social services (language courses, thematic meetings for young people, classes with psychologists, etc.). *"This leads to competition between the library and local youth centres" or "This creates a problem – librarians began to engage in activities that are not typical for this position."*

Researchers record the concern of survey participants and focus groups about the intensifying crisis of disinformation (77.8.1%). Some of the most common examples are all waves of IPSO related to radiation and Actions on the front line in Ukraine. One of the respondents emphasized *"This situation leads to psychological exhaustion, a decrease in the level of critical perception of reality, escalates pessimistic moods and panic expectations."*

This highlights the imperative for libraries to collaborate and form partnerships with the researchers from environmental safety departments, experts from environmental NGOs, and local investigative journalists to dispel IPSO. They will be able to familiarise and train librarians and community members: (1) algorithms for collecting and initially analysing environmental data in extreme conditions of war, (2) open and accessible Citizen Science tools for environmental data in extreme conditions of war. Such a partnership may result in new ideas, practices, and opportunities.

The analysis of the data allowed the researchers to form a conventional list of 5 promising (proactive and reactive) library services that, according to the respondents, will help communities fight disinformation.

Quantitative results and qualitative reflections were combined by the researchers to provide a holistic interpretation of the data. This allowed to draw some conclusions about the processes that can affect the role of libraries in times of crisis and after it. These are **open innovations** and **partnerships**. Although the word "innovation" was not explicitly mentioned in the responses of focus group participants and the survey, the researchers drew attention to the use of synonyms of this word (transformation, adaptation, idea, creativity, change, new services, etc.).

Education, research, and contribution to society through innovation – these are the three missions of HEI, in which libraries are involved as structural units of universities.

The COVID-19 pandemic has become a catalyst for the rapid transition of libraries to online services, potentially affecting the trajectories of innovation. The Russian-Ukrainian war has expanded the vectors of library innovation in the context of open knowledge (from open access resources to Open Science, Open Education and Open Educational Resources) and added social and cultural innovations. As Andreas Schröer (2021) emphasized, the source of new ideas and services are identified new, emergent needs in society or re-conceptualized.

Figure 12. Openness in times of crisis. (Source: Own construction.)

In times of crisis, the university library becomes a centre of open innovations in education, science, social support and culture. It provides open access to digital resources, supports remote learning through OER, promotes academic integrity and media literacy, organizes spaces for psychological relief and trainings for communities on the first medical aid, provides platforms for academic communication, and integrates cultural initiatives to unite the university community and local communities.

Open innovation and partnerships are opportunities that could strengthen the role of libraries in promoting individual and community resilience in times of crisis and beyond.

5. Conclusion and recommendations

This report summarizes a study organized and conducted by the USUST at the national level on changing the roles and expanding the capabilities of university libraries in Ukraine in responding to crises. The researchers relied on responses in an online survey and focus group discussions (for security reasons, it was held online) conducted in May 2025.

The results confirm that, even in moments of turmoil (for Ukrainians, a crisis related to the war), communities of higher education institutions, stakeholders, and urban residents trust and value libraries for the following: • sustainability as reliable centres of access to resources for learning, teaching, researching (online and offline) and to numerous multidirectional services (the nomenclature of which may change situationally); • their efforts to provide safe spaces (physical or digital), where you can not only study, but also feel psychological and academic support, silence, or , in contrast, the joy of communication, the "normality" of life that goes on; • their social initiatives (aimed at supporting vulnerable groups, mental health, inclusion and mutual assistance within the academic community) and volunteer initiatives (to help internally displaced persons, students in difficult circumstances, the military people or communities); • library staff's humanity, competence, and ability to communicate, as well as the ability of libraries to respond to urgent needs, etc.

At the same time, such trust in libraries in crisis is often "passive" in nature, not accompanied by active interaction, participation or recognition within the university (or local community), which leads to an underestimation of the role of the library in the crisis response system. This may indicate a low awareness of the community about the capabilities of libraries, limited visibility of library services, the traditional idea of libraries as comfortable spaces, as well as internal barriers of librarians – personal or professional burnout in conditions of constant danger, lack of competencies or resources to act in crisis conditions.

Because the participants of focus groups, in addition to the academic community, were stakeholders involved in that community with their special view of the situation under study, as well as the obtained quantitative and qualitative data on the combination of efforts of university libraries and representatives of local communities, public associations in supporting communities in crises, the idea of the importance of strengthening cooperation between them, which is currently insufficient, can be traced.

To ensure a holistic interpretation of the data and draw conclusions about the importance of strengthening library cooperation and partnership between academic communities and the public, the researchers combined quantitative results and qualitative reflections. It is assumed that the university library in the conditions of crisis becomes a centre of open innovations in education, science, social support and culture. These open innovations and partnerships can influence the role of libraries in times of

crisis and beyond. These are the opportunities that could strengthen the role of libraries in promoting individual, academic and community resilience in times of crisis and recovery in Ukraine.

Analysis of focus group data and surveys confirms the intensification of the disinformation crisis. Almost 80% of survey respondents report particular demonstrations of IPSO and "waves" of disinformation on topics related to radiation hazard, mobilisation, termination of higher education institutions, emigration processes, war progress, the actions of the population in emergency situations, the socio-economic situation, possible shelling, and events at the front.

This emphasises the need for libraries to partner with environmental safety specialists, public activists, and journalists to counteract IPSO and provide training on collecting and analysing environmental data in wartime settings using the Citizen Science tools. Such cooperation creates space for new solutions and practices.

Based on the results obtained, the researchers emphasise that the crisis has become an impetus for change and offer a list of recommendations to strengthen the role of libraries in promoting individual, academic and community resilience in times of crisis and recovery of Ukraine:

- Increasing visibility and intensifying communications: libraries systematically and actively inform communities about services, events, initiatives through various communication channels;
- Recovering academic communality: • the library becomes one of the key links in maintaining communication and cohesion in the academic community split by the war; • library spaces — a place for authenticity, imagination, cultural dialogue and overcoming the isolation;
- Educational, scientific and emotional support: • the library supports the process of learning, teaching, and research in times of crisis in feasible and safe formats (access to free, verified resources, flexible services, webinars, trainings, etc.); • an enhanced role in creating a safe environment for students, particularly the IDPs;
- Social and inclusive services: • the library offers spaces for mental health support, Internet access, recharging gadgets, volunteer initiatives; • inclusive spaces and digital inclusion services to support people with disabilities.
- Professional training of personnel: development of librarians' competencies in the areas of crisis response, psychological support, digital security, and digital inclusion;
- Expansion of partnerships: the library creates sustainable links with departments, public associations, local media, volunteers, activists of public initiatives, as well as with the international professional community;
- Ensuring resource sustainability: the library plans funding and infrastructure solutions considering crisis scenarios;

- Counteracting disinformation: • cooperation of libraries with researchers of environmental safety departments, experts of environmental public associations, local investigative journalists to dispel IPSO; • training librarians and community members: (1) algorithms for collecting and initial analysis of environmental data in the extraordinary conditions of war, (2) working with open and accessible Citizen Science environmental data tools in the extraordinary conditions of war.

The point of these recommendations is to take an open and "fresh" look at the "key points" that could contribute to expanding the capabilities of university libraries in Ukraine in responding to crisis situations. Of course, we do not have all the answers, but we are open to the implementation of new approaches to improvement and development.

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Annex I

Focus Group Discussion Questions

Background and role

Brief introduction of participants and their role in the academic community.

I Experience with Crisis Contexts

What kinds of crises have you experienced or thought about?

How have these situations affected your research or personal life?

Where would you turn first for help in a crisis, and why?

II Library Roles During Crises

Do you consider libraries as trusted institutions in your community? Why or why not?

Have you ever received help or support from a library during a crisis?

How did the library respond (or could have responded) to the crisis during that time?

III Expectations and Needs

If such a crisis occurred tomorrow, what kind of support would be most important to you?

What would you expect from your library in this situation?

IV Barriers and Gaps

What are the main barriers that prevent libraries from supporting people in this specific crisis?

Are there reasons why you or others might not seek help from a library? If yes, how could we change it?

V Public Engagement & Community Resilience

Can you imagine a library being a place for community action or support? If yes, then how?

In your opinion, how can libraries build stronger communities during or after a crisis?

VI Case Specific Questions - The crisis of disinformation in an emergency

Have you encountered disinformation crises in the last 3 years of the Great War in Ukraine?

Can you give examples of how such disinformation crises have affected you and your family?

What thematic aspects of the disinformation crisis in the extraordinary conditions of the war in Ukraine are the most widespread and relevant?

What role can academic libraries play in preventing, preventing or mitigating the social, civic and political consequences of disinformation?

Annex II

Survey Questions

I Background information

1. Age *(select one option)*

18-25

26-35

36-45

46-60

61+

Prefer not to say

2. Territory of your residence or temporary stay in Ukraine *(select one option)*

South-East Ukraine (Dnipropetrovsk, Zaporizhia regions)

East Ukraine (Donetsk, Luhansk, Kharkiv regions)

South Ukraine (Mykolaiv, Odesa, Kherson regions, Crimea)

North Ukraine (Kiev, Kyiv, Chernihiv, Sumy, Zhytomyr regions)

Center Ukraine (Kirovohrad, Poltava, Vinnytsia, Cherkasy regions)

West Ukraine (Lviv, Ivano-Frankivsk, Chernivtsi, Zakarpattia regions)

North-West Ukraine (Volyn, Rivne, Ternopil, Khmelnytskyi regions)

Other

3. What is your current role within the academic community? *(Select the one you identify with the most)*

Student

Academic staff (e.g., lecturer, researcher)

Library staff

Administrative or support staff

Citizen scientist

I am not a member of the academic community

Other: _____

4. What type of crisis has affected you the most? ((Choose up to FOUR answers that are most relevant to you))

War or armed conflict

Political turbulence

Pandemic or health crisis

Mental health or well-being challenges in academic life

Information overload and challenges related to open science in research

Environmental health and quality crisis

Climate related crisis (e.g., heatwave, drought, flooding)

Disinformation during emergencies (e.g., war, disasters)

Problems with social integration or job opportunities for international students

Barriers faced by disabled people (e.g., access, inclusion)

Other: _____

5. How do you usually find information during a crisis? *(Select all that apply)*

Social media

News media

Government websites

University websites or communication

Friends/family

Library channels

Academic journals or research sources

Other: _____

II Library Roles During Crises

6. Have you ever received support from a library during a crisis? Support could include practical help, information, or emotional support. *(Select one option)*

Yes

No

Not sure

6a. If yes, what kind of support did you receive? *Open question*

7. In a crisis situation, which forms of support would you expect or seek from a library?

(Select all that apply)

Access to curated information

Internet or Wi-Fi

Charging stations

Physical space for study/work

Mental health support or safe environment

Cultural events and social interaction

Help with government forms or aid

Emergency supplies (masks, flashlights, etc.)

Online library services (ebooks, databases, etc.)

Guidance for using academic databases

Training sessions and courses

Support for research or community projects that respond to the crisis

I would not expect anything from a library

Other: _____

III Expectations and Needs

8. When facing a crisis, how important would each of the following be for you personally? Some of these needs may be supported by libraries, others may not. Please rate how important each would be to you personally in a crisis. (Rate each from "Not at all important" to "Very important")

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Important	Very important
Access to credible, accurate, and curated information					
Reliable internet access					
Access to physical space or shelter					
Community connection					

Support for mental health					
Online library access					
Emergency information updates					
Assistance with digital tools					
Being part of the solution					
Opportunities for collaboration or problem-solving with others					
Feeling informed and involved					

9. What would make a library feel like a supportive and safe space during a crisis (e.g., space, staff, resources)? *Open question*

IV Barriers and Support Gaps

10. What might prevent you from using library services in a crisis? *(Select all that apply)*

Library is closed

Difficult to find up-to-date information from the library website and social media channels

Library location is hard to reach

Library is not accessible or inclusive for disabled users

Library has no internet access

Did not know library could help

Negative past experiences at the library

Lack of trust in libraries

Other: _____

11. Would you feel comfortable approaching a library for help in crisis? *(select one option)*

Yes

No

Not sure

11a. If you answered “No” or “Not sure,” please explain why:

Open question

V Public Engagement and Community Support

12. Please rate your agreement with several statements *(Rate the level of your agreement with each of the following statements on a scale from "Strongly disagree" to "Strongly agree")*

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Libraries can play an important role in supporting communities during crises					
Libraries in my community provide services and support during crises					
I have used the services and support of libraries in my community during crises					

13. Have you ever participated in any community-focused events or activities at your university library? *(Select one option)*

Yes

No

Not sure

13a. If yes, what kind of activity or event was it? *Open question*

14. What activities or services could a library offer to support your community in difficult times? *Open question*

VI DISINFORMATION CRISIS IN EMERGENCY CONDITIONS

15. Have you encountered disinformation crises in the last three years of the full-scale war in Ukraine?

Yes

No

I don't know

16. If you answered "Yes" to the previous question, please provide examples of disinformation you have encountered: *Open question*

17. What thematic aspects of the disinformation crisis in the extraordinary conditions of war in Ukraine are the most widespread and relevant? *(Choose up to five of the most relevant and widespread in your opinion)*

The course of the war

Frontline operations in Ukraine

Physical security and threats in the underground

Socio-economic situation

Public actions in emergency situations

Air pollution

Water pollution

Radiation hazard

Pandemic and health crisis

Changes in the academic environment

National and regional politics

International politics

Other:

18. Can you give an example of the impact of the disinformation crisis on you and your family? *(Open question)*

19. What tools can academic libraries use to anticipate, prevent, or mitigate the impact of the disinformation crisis in your community? *(Select all that apply to you)*

Digests and catalogs of reliable information

Collections of open sources of information

Courses on searching and verifying information

Thematic interviews with specialists from the academic community

Information explanations

Instructions for citizens

Thematic announcements

None of the above

Other

20. Do you have any additional thoughts or comments on the topic of this survey? *Open question*